

ATTENUATIVE CAPACITY OF COMPACTED THREE REDDISH BROWN TROPICAL SOILS

¹Bello, A. A. and ²Osinubi, K. J.

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Osun State University, Osogbo, NIGERIA and ²Department of Civil Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, NIGERIA

ABSTRACT

Three compacted reddish brown tropical soils from Ibadan, Southwestern Nigerian, West Africa, were investigated in the laboratory for their suitability as hydraulic barriers for waste containment structure. The key parameters evaluated was the impact of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) landfill leachate on the geotechnical, mineralogical, long-term hydraulic conductivity and sorptive and diffusive properties of the soils. The effective diffusion coefficient D^* value for Na^+ ($2.69 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$) in MP3 increased to a peak value in MP1 ($3.48 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$) with corresponding decrease in tortuosity factor. It can be seen that Na^+ in MP3 increased to 0.29 in MP1. Also, K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Cl^- also follow the same trend. In all, Na cations were found to diffuse faster than other ions including the only anion Cl^- . The effective diffusion coefficients of the cations and anion were found to be in the order of $\text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Cl}^-$. This finding suggests that the soils would be effective hydraulic barriers against the migration of potential contaminants in landfill leachate. It was also found that the presence of kaolinite as the major mineral allowed sorption of the ions that are generally considered conservative in linear-leachate compatibility studies on soils from tropical regions.

KEYWORDS: Attenuative capacity; Hydraulic barriers; Municipal Solid Waste; Long-term hydraulic conductivity; Reddish brown tropical soil

INTRODUCTION

One of the serious and growing potentials problems in Nigeria is the shortage of land for waste disposal. Poor management of waste such as human, biological, agricultural or industrial leads to severe soil and groundwater contamination as well as adverse health effects (Fantola, 1984; Adewuyi, 2004). Although there are some efforts to reduce and recover the waste, disposal in landfills which is still the most common method for facilities began about 3 decades ago and they are employed primarily to protect ground water quality (Osinubi and Kundiri, 2008). Many communities in developing countries such as Nigeria rely on surface and groundwater as a primary source of drinking water of which a variety of threats to its quality exists. Rapid industrial development in developing countries has increased hazardous waste generation several folds. Heavy metals, organic compounds and other toxic effluents continue to be deliberately released into the environment by manufacturing, mining and oil firm. Streams and other sources of domestic water consumption especially those in rural area are now known to have recorded fatal levels of toxicity with attendant risks to human lives (Olajire and Ayodele, 1998; Benson, 1999; Frempong and Yanful, 2006, 2008). Subsurface pollution from these wastes occurs when water that has leached potentially harmful chemical species migrate through these wastes ultimately reaches the environment beneath the waste. The amount and quality of the contaminated water generated by the waste depends primarily on the conditions, the physical and chemical properties of the waste involved. There is still no cost-effective technologies in Nigeria during this environmentally conscious time for the reuse and recycling of municipal solid waste (MSW). Thus, the use of engineered landfills to control and minimize the effects of soil and water pollution is the primary MSW disposal technology being promoted.

Barrier technologies that have been developed are often intimately related to the environmental impact assessment of the proposed facility. Environmental impact assessments are generally driven by regulatory requirements and as a consequence, typical acceptable barrier systems can be expected to vary geological conditions and variations in regulatory requirements (Rowe *et al.*, 1995). However, environmental approval normally requires a thorough assessment of any chosen barrier system particularly with respect to its attenuative behaviour. This is to ensure that such barrier materials would not release harmful chemicals from its matrix to the leachate solution or groundwater environment but rather possess an absorptive or attenuative capacity for critical contaminants such as heavy metals.

Generally, few works have been done on the attenuative capacity of tropical soils because for a particular soil, the type of clay mineral and the percentage of clay-size fractions may significantly affect soil properties including plasticity, structure, strength, and cation and anion exchange capacity. Though, various soils have been used for soil liner- MSW landfill leachate interaction (Fernandez and Quigley, 1985; Thorton *et al.*, 2000; Frempong and Yanful, 2008) but data on the use of reddish brown tropical soil for soil-liner MSW landfill leachate interaction is lacking. Thus, one of the objectives of this study was to determine index and geotechnical properties and mineralogical compositions of the soil. Another one was to examine the impact of MSW landfill leachate on long-term hydraulic conductivity. The capacity of the soils to attenuate leachate constituents such as Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Cl^- , through batch sorption and diffusion tests. Sodium, potassium and magnesium were selected, as they were present at high concentration in the leachate used. Chloride was chosen because of its high mobility and persistence in the environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Soils

The soils used in this study belong to the group of ferruginous tropical soils derived from acid igneous and metamorphic rocks which may either be leached out of the profile or precipitated within it in the form of spots or concretions. They contain mostly kaolinite, residual quartz and free iron oxides (Malomo, 1983). Ferruginous soils occur widely between the 500 and 1200mm isohyets in areas having contrasting wet and dry season regime (Katte, 1996). D'Hoore (1954) also stated that they are usually formed on parent materials rich in quartz, that is, on the crystalline rocks of the basement complex, on granite and many sedimentary deposits but not on volcanic or ultra basic or calcareous rocks. A study of the geological and soil maps of Nigeria (Akintola, 1982 and Areola, 1982) shows that the study area lies within southwestern Nigeria basement complex which forms part of the African crystalline shield.

The soil used in this study is a reddish brown tropical soil from Ibadan, (latitude $7^{\circ}27'$ and longitude $4^{\circ}59'$) Southwestern Nigeria using the method of disturbed sampling. The soil samples were obtained at depths of 0.9 – 2.9m and designated as MP1, MP2 and MP3. The soils are classified as A-7-6 according to the Association of American States Highway and Transportation Officials Classification System and are also classified as lean clay with sand (CL), according to the Unified Soil Classification System (BSI, 1990; Head, 1992). The specific gravity of the soil range from 2.61- 2.64 while its pH range from 6.30 – 7.00. The percentage passing BS No.200 sieve range from 56.15 – 58.99%.

Mineralogical composition test

The mineralogical compositions of the soils were carried out using X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques as outlined by Brown and Brindley (1989). The X-ray diffraction patterns or diffractograms were recorded with a Rigaku Rotating Anode X-ray diffractometer. Powder diffractograms of the soil samples were obtained by scanning the samples at a rate of $10^{\circ}20$ per minute over an angular range of $2-82^{\circ}$. Slides of specimens of the natural soils were prepared from the $<2\mu\text{m}$ size soil fractions of the samples. The slides were subsequently water saturated, air dried, ethylene glycol solvated, and heat treated (at 550°C for 30min) and then scanned to obtain preferred oriented diffractograms. Mineral identification on the diffractograms followed procedures established by Brindley and Brown (1989); Brown and Brindley (1989). The determination of the fabric was carried out by the Field emission scanning electrons microscopy (FESEM) to supplement the X-ray data for mineral identification. Chemical tests result such as Energy dispersive x-ray spectrometry (EDX) and Energy dispersive x-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) were also employed to show the elemental composition of each of the samples. The clay mineralogy of the soil sample using X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out at the Engineering Materials Development Institute (EMDI), Akure, Southwestern Nigeria and Department of Material Science, International Islamic University, Malaysia. FESEM and EDX were also carried out at the International Islamic University of Malaysia.

Hydraulic Conductivity Testing

Compaction was carried out on samples that were previously moistened with tap water and mixed thoroughly, then compacted using the standard Proctor compactive effort. This compactive effort was used to ensure that the quantity of permeant that entered and went through the samples was adequate to interact with the sample in water to establish chemical equilibrium, and that the flow rate was high to ensure that advection was the dominant means of

contaminant transport. Each of the soil samples was compacted at 2% water content wet of optimum water content based on the optimum water contents measured earlier during hydraulic conductivity tests. The samples were then soaked in an immersion tank for a period of 3 days to allow for full saturation and the samples were restrained from swelling vertically during saturation. The hydraulic conductivity was measured using the rigid wall permeameter under falling head condition as recommended by Head (1992). It necessary to state here that flexible wall permeameter supposed to be used but due to its unavailability, the rigid wall one was adopted since it gives a relatively the same result with the flexible wall permeameter. The leachates used for the study were obtained from three different points. Two of it was obtained from Ahmadu Bello, Zaria, Nigeria open dump landfill located behind the Centre for Energy Research and Training while the remaining one was obtained from an open dump behind NUGA gate, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The characteristics of the leachate used are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of MSW leachates used

Parameter	Leachates concentration (mg/l)		
	1	2	3
Calcium, Ca	34.6	28.2	16.3
Potassium, K	179	213	122.3
Magnesium, Mg	37.8	41.7	41.1
Sodium, Na	271.6	315.6	270.8
Iron, Fe	21.8	18.9	15.5
Manganese, Mn	28.3	31.2	22.8
Lead, Pb	0.33	0.68	0.7
Zinc, Zn	23.6	17.8	41.1
Chromium, Cr	0.51	1.1	0.7
Chloride, Cl	357.4	401.8	307.8
Sulphate, SO ₄	154	163	145
Phosphate, P ₂ SO ₄	221	132	256
Nitrate, NO ₃	0.79	1.3	3.1
Hardness	583	324	389
pH	9.1	9.1	8.9
EC, μ mhos/cm	1100	1050	41
TDS	6.9	8.3	6.9

Batch Equilibrium Adsorption Tests

Batch equilibrium adsorption test (BEATS) were performed with the soil samples and the leachate to quantify the potential adsorption of some specified cations, namely' Ca²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ and Mg²⁺. The procedures used for BEATS generally followed those used by Shackelford *et al.* (1989), Shackelford and Daniel (1991) and Cotton *et al* (1998).

A 1:4 (soil – solution ratio) by weight of dry soil), which is the highest recommended ratio (“Batch-type” 1987; Shackelford, 1989) was used in the BEATS. The 1:4 ratio was maintained by adding 50g of soil and 200g of solution into each of eighteen (18) different plastic containers previously raised with distilled water. The concentration of the leachates (3 in number) used varied as shown on Table. The same leachate that was used for compatibility test was also used here with additional two having different chemical composition as shown on leachate on table 3.1. The mixtures were placed in a table shaker (HS 500 Janke and Kunker, Ika-Werk) at a speed of 30 hub/min and allowed to mix for a period of 48 h before obtaining the supernatant by filtering into plastic bottle using filter papers. Cation concentrations were measured using UNICAM 969 Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer (AAS).

The results of the chemical analysis were plotted in the form of adsorption isotherms, or sorbed concentration, C_s, versus dissolved equilibrium concentration, C, of solute for each ion. The sorbed concentration was determined by mass balance using eq. (1).

The solute per mass of solid soil, C_s , is determined from the following equation:

$$C_s = \frac{(C_o - C)V}{M_s}, mg/g \quad (1)$$

Where C_s = adsorbed concentration in microgram per gram;
 C_o = initial concentration of solute;
 C = equilibrium concentration in pore water;
 M_s = mass of soil solids; and
 V = volume of solution.

The slope of the adsorption isotherm (plot of sorbed concentration versus equilibrium concentration), called the partition or partitioning coefficient, K_p , is given by;

$$K_p = \frac{dc_s}{dc} \quad (2)$$

Also,

The partitioning coefficient is used to determine the retardation factor, R_d , by the following equation (Shackelford, 1994b; Shackelford and Daniel, 1991b):

$$R_d = 1 + \frac{\rho_d}{n_e} K_p \quad (3)$$

or

$$R_d = 1 + \frac{\rho_d}{\theta} K_p \quad (4)$$

where ρ_d and n_e are the dry, or bulk density and effective porosity, respectively, of the in situ soil and θ is volumetric water content.

Diffusion testing

The diffusion set-up consists of PVC pipes with height of 20cm and 10cm diameter containing compacted soil samples with a height of 12cm.

Diffusion Specimen Preparation

Each of the soil samples was compacted at 2% water content wet of optimum water content based on the optimum water contents using modified Proctor compactive effort to assume the same volume and density of the specimens used for the clay-leachate compatibility test. Prior to sealing of the top of the cells, distilled water was allowed to pond over the top of each compacted soil sample for at least 40 days. This was done in order to achieve soil saturation and to minimize mass transport of contaminants due to suction in the soil. The distilled water was used to avoid addition of chemical species that may be present in tap water.

Diffusion, Sectioning and Extraction

The diffusion stage of the tests was initiated by gradually introducing the MSW leachate into the cell and ensuring that there were no air bubbles on top of the solution. The chemical species in the leachate were allowed to diffuse into the saturated, compacted soils for three (3) months. At the end of the diffusion stage, each cell (10cm diameter by heights of 20cm, soil thickness maintained at 12cm) was disassembled, and the 12cm thick soil extruded and sectioned into slices of equal dimensions (1.1cm thick).

Sectioning was carried out to provide: (1) a distribution of water contents existing in the specimens by oven-drying, and (2) a concentration profile of the specified cations for use in determining the effective diffusion coefficients. The slices are divided into two portions: one set was used to determine water contents of the slices while the second set of slices was allowed to air-dry prior to extraction. The water contents of the slices were determined by oven-drying.

The air-dried slices for concentration profile determination were digested by adding aqua regia (mixture of HCl and HNO₃ in the ratio of 1:3, that is, 5 ml of HCl to 15ml of HNO₃) into 1g of the soil in a beaker. The material in the beaker was boiled with content stirring for about 30 to 45minutes. After cooling, some distilled water was added to the material in the beaker before being passed through filter paper. The filtrate was collected in a 250 ml volumetric flask and the content was made up to the 250ml mark of the flask. Then, the elemental analysis was carried out using the UNICAM 969 Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS).

The effective diffusion coefficient for each of the sample was calculated using eq. (3.21), with retardation factors (R_d) obtained from the batch equilibrium results and reservoir concentration data taken for $x=0$. The tortuosity factors were obtained by using the self-diffusion coefficients for representative ions at infinite dilution in water (Shackelford and Daniel, 1991).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Index Properties and Chemical Composition

The index properties of the soil samples are summarized in Table 1. The results of the particle size distribution are shown on Fig. 1. The percentage passing the No. 200 sieve ranged between 59.2 and 66.4% while the clay (percentage passing 2 μ m) presents fall between 21.57 and 25.39% for the soil specimen. Appreciable quantities of fines in a given soil are required for soils that will serve as hydraulic barrier materials. The plasticity indices generally ranged between 14 and 16% while the activity of the soils is in the range of 0.60 and 0.67. These values of activity, A, (plasticity index, PI/clay fraction) are typical of those often reported for Kaolinitic soils (Mitchell, 1976; Holtz and Kovacs, 1981; Oweis and Khera, 1998). All the soil samples are classified as A-7-6 according to the AASHTO classification system; also the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) classifies the samples as CL, which is an indication of low plasticity clay (Bowles, 1992; Coduto, 2003; Punmia *et al.*, 2005). On the basis of the Casagrande's plasticity chart, these soils are inorganic clays of low to medium plasticity or sandy silty clays (Holtz and Kovacs, 1981). According to the engineering use chart (Wagner, 1957; Lambe and Whitman, 1979), these soils are impervious with respect to their permeability when compacted. The soils should be of medium compressibility when compacted and saturated and should be of good to fair workability as construction materials.

The grading modulus was calculated from the expression (TRRL, 1990):

$$\text{Grading modulus} = \frac{300 - (\% < 2.00\text{mm} + \% < 425\mu\text{m} + \% < 75\mu\text{m})}{100} \quad (5)$$

It has been shown by Osinubi (2002) that grading characteristics of a soil can be characterized by its grading modulus from 0.61 and 0.76. In this study, percentage of soil fraction passing the 2.40mm sieve was used instead of 2.00mm sieve. It was the one available in the laboratory at the time of the experimental programme and the two sizes are interchangeably used in practice. The plasticity product is defined as the plasticity index multiplied by the soil fraction passing 75 μ m. The plasticity modulus is the product of the plasticity index and the percentage of soil fraction passing 425 μ m (CIRIA, 1988). These terms are often used to show the contribution of the soil's plasticity and particle size distribution to its behavior. The index properties of the soil samples which were obtained in accordance with procedures outlined in BS 1377 (1990) as well as its oxide composition are presented in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. The oxide and trace element compositions of the soils are as presented. Silica and sesquioxides of aluminium and iron are the dominant oxides in the clays, constituting approximately 77-89% of the oxides present.

Table2. Summary of Properties of soil samples

Properties	Soil		
	MP1	MP2	MP3
Natural moisture content, %	5.2	5.9	5.6
Specific gravity	2.66	2.62	2.65
Liquid limit, %	43	48	44
Plastic limit, %	29	32	28
Plasticity index, %	14	16	16
Linear shrinkage, %	8.6	7.80	6.25
% Passing BS No. 40 sieve	80.1	77.25	81.55
% Passing BS No. 200 sieve	63.55	59.2	66.4
% < 2 μm	23.63	21.52	25.39
AASHTO classification	A - 7 - 6	A - 7 - 6	A - 7 - 6
USCS classification	CL	CL	CL
Group index	8	9	9
Activity	0.55	0.68	0.74
Derived parameters			
Grading modulus	0.61	0.67	0.60
Plasticity product	889.7	947.2	982.4
Plasticity modulus	1121.4	1236.0	1304.8

Table3. Chemical composition of soil samples

Oxides	Soil		
	MP1	MP2	MP3
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	9.2	7.7	8.2
CaO (%)	4.3	4.1	7.2
MnO ₃ (%)	0.31	0.10	0.35
K ₂ O (%)	1.0	0.6	1.6
Cr ₂ O ₃ (%)	0.12	0.13	0.3
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	5.1	3.3	4.1
SiO ₂ (%)	3.4	5.7	2.2
K (ppm)	209	915	910
Ca (ppm)	155	667	331
Cr (ppm)	11.2	12.4	10.6
Mn (ppm)	7.8	2.46	16.8
Fe (ppm)	459	189	334
Ni (ppm)	21.0	-	21.7
Cu (ppm)	14.8	14.5	15.2
Zn (ppm)	10.8	10.2	10.3
Pb (ppm)	10.7	7.67	11.5
Organic Carbon	0.13	0.18	0.11
U(ppm)	3.87	-	4.54
pH	6.10	6.20	6.20
EC $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$	0.29	0.26	0.16

Fig. 1: Particle-size distribution curves for the soil samples

Mineralogical Composition

It was found out that the specimens consist of Kaolinite as their major clay minerals with other minerals such as quartzite, halloysite and muscovite. This was backed up with the fabric/structure test which was carried out by the Field emission scanning electrons microscopy (FESEM) at the same department in the International Islamic University, Malaysia. FESEM has been reported to be 6 times better than the scanning electron microscopy. The FESEM micrograph shows that Kaolitic flakes and halloysitic flakes are visible in sample specimen (see Plates 1-3). By this, there are visible flocs which seem to be sandy silt- sized particles. The fabric of a soil refers to the geometric arrangement of particles (Holtz and Kovacs, 1981).

a

b

c

d

Plates 4.1 a, b, c and d: Micrographs showing Kaolinitic and Halloysitic flakes at 10,000, 20,000, 50,000 and 100,000 magnification using FESEM for MP1

Plates 4.2 a, b, c and d: Micrographs showing Kaolinitic and Halloysitic flakes at 10,000, 20,000, 50,000 and 100,000 magnification using FESEM for MP2

Plates 4.3 a, b, c and d: Micrographss showing Kaolinitic and Halloysitic flakes at 10,000, 20,000, 50,000 and 100,000 magnification using FESEM for MP3

Hydraulic Conductivity Testing

The results of the experiment are shown in Fig.4. The general trend was that of slight increase in hydraulic conductivity with increased permeation period. When the samples were permeated with water hydraulic conductivity increased from $7.03 \times 10^{-8} - 7.94 \times 10^{-8}$, $7.50 \times 10^{-8} - 8.35 \times 10^{-8}$ and $2.40 \times 10^{-8} - 2.99 \times 10^{-8}$ for MP1, MP2 and MP3 respectively while the with the addition of MSW leachate the hydraulic conductivity decreased prominently for some days and slightly decreased non uniformly in all the samples from $7.22 \times 10^{-8} - 6.12 \times 10^{-8}$, $7.50 \times 10^{-8} - 6.49 \times 10^{-8}$ and $2.50 \times 10^{-8} - 1.75 \times 10^{-8}$ for MP1, MP2 and MP3. During permeation with tap water, the hydraulic conductivity increased by 1.13, 1.12 and 1.25 for MP1, MP2 and MP3 respectively. Permeating with MSW leachate lead to a decrease in hydraulic conductivity by about 1.18, 1.16 and 1.42orders of magnitude for AB1, AB2and AB3 respectively. This result is in agreement with earlier works by Shackelford (1994), Rowe *et al.* (1995) as well as Osinubi and Nwaiwu (2006) stated that MWS leachate could cause a slight decrease in the hydraulic conductivity of inactive clays probably due to Na^+ adsorption and double-layer expansion and also due to bacteria clogging.

Fig. 5: Variation of Hydraulic conductivity with time on MP1, MP2 and MP3 samples

Batch Equilibrium

The result of the batch equilibrium test for all these soil samples show trends of chemical sorption for Sodium (Na^+), Calcium (Ca^+), Magnesium (Mg^{2+}) and Potassium (K^+) as shown in Figs.6-12 respectively. The cations were so selected because they represent the dominant and critical contaminants in the leachate. All the adsorption isotherms exhibit a linear trend though negative for all the cations. This is in agreement with the observations of Rowe *et al.* (1995) that linear isotherms are reasonable representations of the adsorption of contaminants found in leachate from municipal waste disposal sites where concentrations are often relatively low. The distribution coefficient, K_d , that is a key parameter in the assessment of the adsorption behaviour of a barrier material is expressed as (Rowe *et al.*, 1995).

$$K_d = \frac{(C_o - C) \frac{V}{M_s}}{C_f}, \text{ ml/g} \quad (6)$$

Also, the distribution coefficient, K_d can be obtained from the resulting slopes. The distribution coefficient K_d known as the partition coefficient, K_p was used in obtaining the retardation factor (R_d) as shown in eq. (6)

Fig. 6: Adsorption Isotherms for MP1 (for all ionic species)

Fig 7: Adsorption Isotherms for MP2 (for all ionic species)

Fig 8: Adsorption Isotherms for MP3 (for all ionic species)

Fig 9: Adsorption Isotherms for Na⁺ (all MP soils)

Fig 10: Adsorption Isotherms for Ca²⁺ (all MP soils)

Fig 11: Adsorption Isotherms for Mg²⁺ (all MP soils)

Fig 12: Adsorption Isotherms for K⁺ (all MP soils)

The values of K_d or K_p obtained range from 1.56 - 1.96 ml/g for Na^+ (for MP1 to MP3), 2.88 - 4.17 ml/g for Ca^{2+} , 6.91 - 7.52 ml/g for Mg^{2+} , and 4.52 - 4.80 ml/g. Their corresponding retardation factors, also shown in Table 4, were calculated using eq. (4), and range from 4.30 - 3.73 for Na^+ , 7.57 - 5.50 for Ca^{2+} , 9.98 - 8.93 for Mg^{2+} , and 5.92 - 5.37 for K^+ . All the values obtained are within the ranges got by other researchers (Nwaiwu, 2004; Shackleford *et al.*, 1997).

As the values of plasticity product decreases from 982.3 (MP3) to 889.2 (MP1). K_p values increases while R_d values decreases correspondingly. It could be seen that all the values of the retardation factor are greater than 1.0, therefore, a process of ionic retardation or attenuation must have taken place within the abandoned dumpsite soil.

Table 4. Retardation Factors for sample specimen

Soil sample	Na^+	Retardation Factor, R_d		
		Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}	K^+
MP1	3.73	5.50	8.93	5.37
MP2	3.78	6.75	9.39	5.90
MP3	4.30	7.57	9.95	5.92

The results presented in Table 4 also show the following species sorption selectivity order: $Na^+ < K^+ < Ca^{2+} < Mg^{2+}$. The sorption selectivity order obtained in all the soil specimens is consistent with results reported for other tropical soils (Frempong and Yanful, 2008).

Diffusion Test Results

The variation of water content with depth for each slice of soil sample after the 90 days diffusion testing is shown in Figs 13 for the soils samples. The water contents determined are weighted averages.

Fig. 13: Variation of water content with depth after diffusion testing for soil samples.

Fig. 14: Ion concentration –depth profile for MP1

The ion concentration-depth profiles got for the samples are shown in Figs. 14-16. MP1, MP2 and MP3 respectively while the concentration profiles for the chemical species (Cl^- , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+}) are shown in 17-20.

Fig. 15: Ion concentration –depth profile for MP2

Fig. 16: Ion concentration –depth profile for MP3

Fig. 17: Ion concentration –depth profile for Chlorine

Fig. 18: Ion concentration –depth profile for Sodium

Fig. 19: Ion concentration –depth profile for Potassium

Fig. 20: Ion concentration –depth profile for Magnesium

Shackelford *et al.* (1997) stated that one analytical solution to Fick’s second law for one-dimensional diffusion through saturated soil for the case of a decreasing source concentration and for finite cell length is

$$\frac{c(x \geq 0, t)}{c_0} = \frac{\alpha}{1 + \alpha} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\alpha}{1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 q^2 m} \exp\left(\frac{-D^* q^2 m t}{R_d L^2}\right) \frac{\cos[q_m(1 - x/L)]}{\cos(q_m)} \quad (7)$$

Where C_0 = the initial concentration of the solute in the source reservoir, D^* = the effective diffusion coefficient ($=\tau D_0$) where D_0 is the free-solution diffusion coefficient, which expresses in quantitative terms, the rate at which a diffusion process occurs (Shackelford *et al.*, 1989), R_d = the retardation factor for linear, instantaneous, and reversible sorption, L = the length of the soil specimen, and x = the direction of diffusive transport.

The effective diffusion coefficient D^* were obtained using equation 7, is shown in table 5 and 6. They fall within the range reported by Shackelford and Redmond (1995). Generally, the D^* value for of Na^+ ($2.69 \times 10^{-10} m^2/s$) in MP3 increased to a peak value in MP1 ($3.48 \times 10^{-10} m^2/s$) with corresponding decrease in tortuosity factor. K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Cl^- also follow the same trend for the soil sample. It can be seen that Na^+ (0.18) in MP3 increased to 0.29 in MP1 (highest plasticity product). It can also be seen that K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Cl^- also follow the same trend. The gradual increase in the D^* values seems to reflect the difference in the plasticity product of the soils. The greater the plasticity product (highest for MP2), the lower the D^* for all chemical species including the only anion tested for (Cl^-). It can also be noticed that the greater the plasticity product the higher the turtuosity factor. It is to be noted that the presence of Na^+ in a high percentage in any soil normally leads to the dispersion of the soil particles, which is a very detrimental problem in compacted soil liners and other related geotechnical engineering matters. The

percentage of Na⁺ gotten from diffusion tests and batch equilibrium tests were not high, thus there was no record of alarming level of Na⁺ presence. As a result of this, the sample specimen used in this research work can be considered for liner materials.

The tortuosity factor, τ , obtained ranges from 0.18 - 0.45 for soil samples. All the values are within the range of 0.1 to 0.58 for natural soil reported by Daniel and Shackelford (1988). As the plasticity product increases, the values for tortuosity factor and effective diffusion coefficient increases, highlighting the importance of soil compositional factors in the natural soil attenuation.

Table 5. Soil profile Diffusion Coefficients (m²/s)

Chemical Specie	MP1	Soil	
		MP2	MP3
Na ⁺	3.48	2.99	2.67
K ⁺		3.64	3.15
Mg ²⁺	4.72	3.84	2.87
Cl ⁻		4.97	4.03
			3.14

Table 6. Soil profile Tortuosity factor, τ_a

Chemical Specie	MP1	Soil	
		MP2	MP3
Na ⁺	0.46	0.32	0.41
K ⁺	0.38	0.26	0.30
Mg ²⁺	0.37	0.29	0.34
Cl ⁻	0.45	0.37	0.41

CONCLUSIONS

The characteristics of reddish brown tropical soils from Ibadan, Southwestern Nigeria, West Africa, and their interactions with MSW landfill leachate, have been studied. It was revealed from the result of compaction test that maximum dry density increased but moisture water content decreased as fines content, plasticity product as well as plasticity modulus increased and grading modulus decreased.

It was established that sorption capacities and processes are influenced by the chemical composition of the soil notably, mineralogy as well as the chemical constituents of the source leachate. However, soils used in this study are compatible with the municipal solid waste leachate. Compatibility test values showed that the hydraulic conductivities of soil samples generally decreased with increasing time indicating that the soils are compatible with municipal solid waste leachate. Retardation factors (R_a) of Mg²⁺ is highest for the samples while Na⁺ is lowest for all the samples based on batch equilibrium adsorption tests and are generally within the range found in the literature. The effective diffusion coefficients and tortuosity factors determined from the diffusion tests were within the range found in the literature. The study also showed that the sorption behaviors of soil samples are a function of the plasticity product. Retardation factors increase with increasing values in plasticity product while effective diffusion coefficient and tortuosity factors decrease with increasing values of plasticity product which is still in line with what is found in literature.

The effective diffusion coefficient D^* value for Na⁺ ($2.69 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$) in MP3 increased to the highest value in MP1 ($3.48 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$) with corresponding decrease in tortuosity factor. It can be seen that Na⁺ (0.18) in MP3 increased to 0.29 in MP1 (highest plasticity product) . It can also be seen that K⁺, Mg²⁺ and Cl⁻ also follow the same trend. In all, Na cations were found to diffuse faster than other ions including the only anion Cl. The effective diffusion coefficients of the cations and anion were found to be in the order of Na⁺ < K⁺ < Mg²⁺ < Cl⁻. Thus, it could be understood that molecular diffusion controls transport in low hydraulic conductivity materials. The gradual increase in the D^* values seems to reflect the difference in the plasticity product of the soils. The greater the plasticity product (highest for MP1), the lower the D^* for all chemical species including the only anion tested for (Cl⁻). It can also be noticed that the greater the plasticity product the higher the tortuosity factor.

It is to be noted that the presence of Na⁺ in a high percentage in any soil normally leads to the dispersion of the soil particles, which is a very detrimental problem in compacted soil liners and other related geotechnical engineering matters. The percentage of Na⁺ gotten from diffusion tests and batch equilibrium tests were not high, thus there was no record of alarming level of Na⁺ presence. As a result of this, the sample specimen used in this research work can be considered for liner materials and other geotechnical engineering designs without the fear of soil dispersion.

The tortuosity factor, τ , obtained ranges from 0.18 - 0.45 for the soil samples. All the values are within the range of 0.1 to 0.58 for natural soil. Hence, this makes it to be a non reactive soil. As the plasticity product increases, the values for tortuosity factor and effective diffusion coefficient decreases, highlighting the importance of soil compositional factors in natural soil attenuation.

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Corresponding Author

Bello, A. A.

Department of Civil Engineering, Osun State University, Osogbo, NIGERIA

Email: adefemisola@yahoo.com